

MORPHOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF MICROSTRUCTURE FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Ryszard Pyrz
Institute of Mechanical Engineering
University of Aalborg, Pontoppidanstræde 101
DK-9220 Aalborg Ø, Denmark

ABSTRACT

Spatial statistics methods have been used to analyze the pattern of fibers in unidirectional composite materials. By introducing second-order statistical functions and the Dirichlet tessellation, the spatial distribution of fibers has been investigated. The analysis has been performed for several simulated distributions as well as for two distributions of fibers in composite materials having the same constituents but differently manufactured. A simple micromechanical model illustrates an influence of the fibers distribution on calculated stress field.

Keywords: morphology, microstructure, distribution of fibers, statistical functions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The properties of two phase composite materials depend on the properties of each phase and on the geometry and geometrical arrangement of two phases in the material. Whilst the properties of phases are fixed by their constitution, geometrical arrangements are technologically variable. Experimentally determined property values are usually presented in terms of their variation with volume fraction of the dispersed phase, which is merely a statement of the overall composition of the material rather than of its dispersion characteristics. Modelling of a microstructure has customarily been based on the assumption that the microstructure is either perfectly regular or completely random, and such models are exclusively used in the unit cell calculation's strategy for the prediction of overall properties [1]. However, a few real microstructures are regular or completely random. More often we have to deal with disordered microstructures and a descriptive framework for characterising such microstructures is necessary.

2. STATISTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

For demonstration purposes, fibers that appear on the transverse section of unidirectional composites are represented by centre points defined by their coordinates within an observation area A

2.1 Dirichlet tessellation and statistical functions.

Given N distinct fibers in a planar area we can assign to each fiber all points which are nearest to it. This is achieved by drawing the midperpendiculars to the segments joining any two neighbouring fibers. In this way, for each fiber a unique cell is constructed and defined as the smallest convex polygon surrounding it, which contains all points in the planar area that are closer to a given fiber than to any other. This polygonal tessellation, the Dirichlet tessellation [2], covers the plane of observation without overlapping.

The description of the basic properties of a point process that represents the distribution of fibers may be performed with the function K(r). Its theoretical background has been established in [3]. If N_A denotes the mean number of points per unit area then N_A · K(r) is the expected number of further points within radial distance r of an arbitrary point in the observation area A. The practical way of calculation of the function K(r) is shown in [4]. The behaviour of the K(r) function may be used to discriminate among different point patterns. All possible point patterns lie between two extremes: regular pattern and completely random pattern called the Poisson distribution. The set of points is completely random if points are placed in an area where each possible location for a point is equally likely to be chosen, and the location of each point is independent of the location of any other point. The theoretical value of the function K(r) for the Poisson pattern is πr². Introducing a square root transformation of K(r) as

$$L(r) = (\pi^{-1} \cdot K(r))^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{1}$$

the graph of the L(r) versus r for the Poisson process appears as a straight line L(r) = r. Functions L(r) for clustered point patterns will be higher than r and less than r for more ordered patterns. Similar discrimination properties are characteristic for the function K(r) itself [5].

A point pattern such as given by fibers distribution in composite materials can be further described by the pair correlation function g(r) which play a role similar to the variance in a classical analysis of random variables. Considering two infinitesimal areas dA₁ and dA₂ in the plane of observation that are separated by the distance r of their midpoints, the probability p(r) of finding a point in both areas is given by

$$p(r) = g(r) \cdot N_A^2 \cdot dA_1 \cdot dA_2 \tag{2}$$

In physical terms a local maxima of the pair correlation function g(r) determine the most frequent distances between points whereas a local minima correspond to the least frequent distances in the pattern. The functions g(r) and K(r) are related as follows

$$g(r) = (2\pi r)^{-1} \frac{dK(r)}{dr} \tag{3}$$

For the completely random point pattern the theoretical value of the pair correlation function g(r) is equal one.

2.2 Simulated distributions of fibers.

Computer simulations of 100 points with calculated Dirichlet tessellations and corresponding pair correlation functions are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Simulated point patterns.

The size of the square frame corresponds to 512 non-scaled pixels. The hard-core model arose by the imposition of a minimum permissible distance between any two points which were distributed randomly otherwise. This inhibition distance is clearly visible in the corresponding plot of the $g(r)$ function. The single cluster pattern was created by placing randomly half of the points in a pre-determined circular area with the remaining points as a random background. Characteristic distances between points of each pattern are detected by the pair correlation function $g(r)$.

The function $L(r)$ for the hard-core model lies below respective line for the Poisson pattern indicating certain degree of regularity at least for distances indicated in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. Plot of the $L(r)$ function.

The single cluster model is recognized by far higher values of $L(r)$ than for the Poisson pattern. The regular pattern exhibits characteristic "stair" shape function $L(r)$ where each stair corresponds to the deterministic interpoint distances.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Experimental results.

The material used in the analysis was a unidirectional glass-epoxy composite consisting of 8 layers and having total thickness 1 mm. One batch of specimens was manufactured without a pressure (in a sequel called material A) whereas a second batch was subjected to a pressure recommended by the supplier, material B. The position of fibers were detected by the image analysis system QUANTIMET 570 and used as a basis for tessellation calculations, Figure 3. The size of the inner measure frame is 385 μm . Clustering tendency of the fibers in material A as indicated by a matrix rich area in Figure 3 results from insufficient penetration of fibers due to the absence of a pressure, Figure 4. Material A shows both short-range and long-range clustering as the $L(r)$ function remains above the Poisson line for larger r (not shown in the figure). Material B is characterized by a random distribution at distances 50 μm . For larger distances also material B exhibits slight clustering. Characteristic distances are very similar for both materials as can be seen from the plot of the pair correlation function.

Figure 3. Pattern of fibers and the Dirichlet tessellations for material A (above) and material B (below).

Figure 4. $L(r)$ and $g(r)$ functions for material A and B.

3.2 Pairwise interaction between fibers.

In order to illustrate the influence of fibers' distribution on pairwise interaction effects a pair of circular fibers of radius a are embedded in an infinite matrix and subject to the radial displacement at infinity. The distance between centres of fibers is denoted by ρ . The stress imposed on the reference fiber comes from deformation of the matrix at infinity and the disturbance of the stress field by the neighbouring fiber. This reflection, disturbance stress has been calculated in [4] and is expressed as follows

$$\sigma_B = 2N_A \int_{2a}^{\infty} \int_0^{\pi} 8m_o C E \frac{a^4}{\rho^4} f_N(\rho) f_o(\theta) d\theta d\rho \quad (4)$$

where

$$C = \frac{k_1 - k_o}{k_1 + m_o}, \quad E = \frac{k_o(m_1 - m_o)}{2m_1 m_o + k_o(m_1 + m_o)}$$

and k_o, m_o, k_1, m_1 are bulk and shear moduli for the matrix and fibers, respectively. The angle θ determines angular position of disturbing fiber with respect to the reference fiber. Functions $f_N(\rho)$ and $f_o(\theta)$ are probability density functions for nearest neighbour distances and orientations for materials under consideration, Figure 5.

Figure 5. Probability density functions.

These functions have been calculated from statistical analysis of the Dirichlet tessellations as follows [4,5]. Arbitrary polygon of the tessellation uniquely determines the nearest- and near neighbour distances and their orientation for each fiber of the pattern. Thus cumulative distribution functions of distances and orientations may be computed for the observation area. These functions give a number of fibers that have distances or orientations less than or equal to a certain preselected distance or orientation. Direct differentiation of cumulative distribution functions provide respective probability density functions.

For comparative studies the stress (4) has been calculated for uniform, band-limited probability density functions

$$f_N(\rho) = \frac{1}{\rho_{\max} - \rho_{\min}} \quad , \quad f_o(\theta) = \frac{1}{\pi} \quad (5)$$

where ρ_{\max} and ρ_{\min} are the maximum and minimum value of detected nearest neighbour distances and orientations for each material. The area under the uniform probability density functions must be equal to the respective area under the probability density functions for real materials in order to assure that the number of fibers in a hypothetical uniform distribution is the same as in the observed pattern.

The reflection bulk stress (4) is shown in Figure 6. As expected, the reflection stress for material A is significantly smaller than for material B which is the result of an appearance of matrix rich areas.

Figure 6. Reflection stress.

The number of fibers that mostly contribute to the reflection stress i.e. fibers with small and intermediate nearest neighbour distances is lower for material A than for material B. On the other hand, the calculation based upon the assumption of the uniform distribution (5) overestimates the reflection stress as compared with real materials. This is because the uniform distribution usually have more fibers with smallest nearest neighbour distances than corresponding non-uniform distribution with the same number of fibers.

3.3 Conclusion.

The procedure based upon a construction of the Dirichlet tessellation and utilization of the statistical functions $K(r)$, $L(r)$ and $g(r)$ allows to qualify and discriminate different patterns of fibers and provides the means for calculation of important factors which characterize a microstructure. The forms of these functions correspond to various properties of the underlying point pattern. Which function is to be preferred depends mainly on a particular application of information provided by them. Both $K(r)$ and $L(r)$ discriminate between different patterns of fibers and are able to detect small differences in the distribution that could be overlooked otherwise. The transformation (1) has the obvious advantage of linearizing the plot of $K(r)$ for the Poisson point process. The pair correlation function $g(r)$ characterizes the frequency of interpoint distances indicated by its local maxima. For very large values of the radial distance r the pair correlation function tends to one for any homogeneous pattern. If $g(r) = 0$ then the interpoint distance r does not exist.

It should be noted that the distinction between different patterns is distance dependent. Distribution of fibers quantified by the function $K(r)$ or $L(r)$ may be on more regular side of the completely random in one interval and have clustering tendency in another interval. Thus the classification of patterns depends on the distance at which the pattern is sampled.

References

1. Brockenbrough, J.R., Suresh, S., Wienecke, H.A., Deformation of Metal-Matrix Composites with Continuous Fibers: Geometrical Effects of Fiber Distribution and Shape, *Acta metall. mater.*, Vol. 39, pp. 735-752, 1991.
2. Getis, A., Boots, B., *Models of Spatial Processes*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1978.
3. Ripley, B.D., Modelling Spatial Patterns, *J. Roy. Statist. Soc., Ser. B*, Vol. 39, pp. 172-212, 1977.
4. Pyrz, R., Quantitative Description of Composites' Microstructure. Part I: Morphology of Unidirectional Composite Systems, to appear in *J. Comp. Sci. Techn.*, 1993.
5. Pyrz, R., Stereological Quantification of the Microstructure Morphology for Composite Materials, to appear in *Optimal Design with Advanced Materials*, ed. P. Pedersen, Elsevier Applied Science, 1993.